

Towards a Real Comprehension of Social Networks Effects on Cybermedia Web Traffic: Quantitative Impact in the 27 European Union Countries Most Popular Online Journals

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Abstract

Scientific literature pays considerable attention to the study of development and consolidation of social networks in general and their influence on the information industry and journalism in particular. However, there are no global studies on their quantitative impact on the web traffic of cybermedia. This article focuses on this aspect and examines the impact that social networks have on the overall web traffic generated by the cybermedia of the 27 countries that are currently part of the European Union. For this purpose, the five cybermedia with the highest number of unique visitors in each country were selected and, using a tool such as SimilarWeb that considers flows from desktop and laptop computers, a set of variables referring directly or indirectly to social networks were analyzed, comparing this magnitude with those corresponding to direct traffic and search procedures. The data obtained allow us to conclude that of the total web traffic generated among the European Union cybermedia with the highest number of unique visitors, only 9.858% is directly attributable to social networks, a figure lower than magnitudes such as direct traffic (54.493%) or search procedures (26.041%). With percentage differences, this situation is applicable to all 27 countries examined and calls into question aspects such as the large amount of human and economic resources that the information industry allocate to the management social networks and the constant debate generated around the impact that they have on the shaping of public opinion and their incidence in phenomena such as disinformation or disintermediation.

Introduction

Although some significant examples of online social networks already appeared at the end of the 20th century (Classmate, 1995; AsianAvenue, 1997; Sixdegrees, 1997), it was not until the beginning of the 21st century when social networks growth and consolidation took place among the Internet community (Ryze, 2001; LinkedIn, 2002; Tribe, 2002; MySpace, 2003; Xing, 2003, initially under OpenBC name; Orkut, 2004; Flickr, 2004; Facebook, 2004; YouTube, 2005; Reddit, 2005; Twitter, 2006; Pinterest, 2010; or Instagram, 2010).

In just a decade we have seen its implementation and popularization, a circumstance that favors the emergence of a profuse and very varied nature scientific bibliography, ranging from the analysis of its impact on public opinion in general and Internet users in particular until its incardination in phenomena such as Web 2.0, consolidation of prosumer or digital transformation, among others.

Literature Review

Cross-sectional

Starting from the theory of the six degrees of separation exposed in 1929 by Frigyes Karinthy in his short story *Láncszemek*, Watts (2003) highlights how any citizen is connected with another person through no more than five intermediaries or six links and how the number of individuals with whom a person relates increases as the number of links in the chain increases, giving way to an extensive multi-sectorial

production that approaches the phenomenon from a very diverse perspective, ranging from its contribution to the creation of a peculiar scenario of links between individuals in the medium and long term (Liben-Nowell and Kleinberg, 2007) to its role as a formula for alleviating individual isolation in an environment such as the COVID-19 pandemic (Kunelius, 2020; Luengo and García Marín, 2020), passing through specific aspects such as educational (Kezar, 2014; Imlawi, Gregg, and Karimi, 2015; Mishra, 2020), health-related (Luceri, Braun, and Giordano, 2019; Wegmann and Brand, 2019; Smith et al., 2020) or occupational (Bailey et al., 2018; Zivnuska et al., 2019; Acquisti and Fong, 2020), among others.

Sometimes it is alluded to their capacity for the dissemination of antisocial messages or hate speech (Chetty and Alathur, 2018; Alkiviadou, 2019; Bartal, Pliskin, and Ravid, 2019), on other occasions their role as enablers and sustainers of a novel social warp different from the traditional one is highlighted (Kaur et al., 2018; Church, Thambusamy, and Nemati, 2020) and even in certain cases their growing impact on citizens' sexual habits is emphasized (Traeen et al., 2018).

No lesser, neither in quantity nor in relevance, is the flow of works referring to the insertion of social networks in an environment such as Web 2.0 or that underline the increase in their transcendence as a consequence of the consolidation of the prosumer of all types of content or that highlight their imbrication in the phenomenon of digital transformation. The first of these approaches is reinforced by the consolidation of the manual semantic web, considered not only as a strategic way of showing how the network to which users were accustomed is being transformed both in its interfaces and in the visualization of its contents (DiNucci, 1999) but also as its changing as a great agora where Internet users from all over the world establish a conversation on a global scale in which they share all kinds of contents including journalistic ones (O'Reilly, 2005), with contributions referring to the use of social networks as marketing tools placed at the service of specific productive sectors (Gibreel, Al Otaibi, and Altmann, 2018) but also with those that delve into their dimension as collaborative learning platforms (Nasrir Ansari, and Khan, 2020) or as creators of certain states of opinion that influence electoral consultations in democratic societies (Kahne and Bowyer, 2018).

These proposals are also outlined through the figure of the prosumer in its aspect of producer and creator of content (Toffler, 1980; Kotler, 1986; Ritzer and Jurgenson, 2010) highlighting subjects such as the capacity to generate topics of the most varied nature (Bird, 2011), segmentation according to population groups (Olin-Scheller and Wikström, 2010; Martínez-Sala, Segarra, and Monserrat, 2018), the influencer phenomenon (Garibay et al., 2019; Hughes, Swaminathan, and Brooks, 2019; Zhuang, Li, and Zhuang, 2021) or everything that has to do with the implementation of crowdfunding projects (Fanea-Ivanovici, 2019; Clauss et al. 2020).

In the case of digital transformation, understood as a new conception of a multisectoral and disruptive nature that goes beyond the merely technological and affects all vital areas of people and organizations and modifies traditional work procedures, leisure habits, personal interrelationships or business models (Barland, 2013; Guo and Volz, 2019) we notice a wide range of analyses on aspects that correspond to its use by public authorities as an element of social control (Chen and Grossklags, 2022) as well as those

focused on its contribution to the disruption of business models (Kotarba, 2018) and the promotion of practices related to entrepreneurship (Bican and Brem, 2020).

Information industry

Similarly, the scientific literature pays considerable attention to the particular case of the information industry, with five main lines of research, often combined and interconnected with each other: the influence of social networks in the information ecosystem; their repercussion on the set of processes that take part of the productive structure of the mass media; the specific impact they have on the information professionals who work in these media; their incidence on the audiences who consume journalistic contents; and their use for channeling all kinds of hoaxes and false contents by national and supranational institutions, local and multinational private corporations and lobbying groups operating on a national and transnational scale.

The first of these is addressed in works that emphasize their facet as platforms on which the ecosystem of the information industry is based (Campos et al., 2016) or in their capacity to influence journalistic deontology (Singer, 2012) and even by institutions that highlight their ability to influence younger audiences, which makes them abandon the habit of consulting the media to access news (European Commission, 2020), and their contribution to undermine the moral authority of the media in the eyes of public opinion (UNESCO, 2020) or corporate entities pointing out the unreliability of much of the content circulating through them (International Federation of Journalists, 2021) as well as their contribution to the spread of populisms (Reuters Institute, 2019) and to the process of media disintermediation (World Association of Newspapers and News Publishers, 2022).

In the same sense, the inputs that have to do with its nature as a competitor of the information industry are relevant, both in its side of contributing to a modification of the tempo of the information flow (Hermida et al., 2012) as well as in that related to its capacity to gradually undermine the influence of the media on public opinion (Meraz, 2011; Choi, 2016) or in that which has to do with rivalry in the search for revenue from advertisers (Franklin, 2012; Tomyuk and Avdeeva, 2022) or even from investment funds (Weber, Fulk, and Monge, 2016).

The area of research on the impact of social networks on the productive structure of the media is approached taking into account factors such as their contribution to the changes in the model itself that involves the promotion of practices like hyperlinking and cyber-banning (Costera Meijer and Groot Kormelink, 2015), those referring to their effects on sponsored content (Serazio, 2020) or those that impact their role in prolonging the traditional news production cycle (Goode 2009; Anderson 2013).

Also noteworthy are works that have to do with their effects on specific media or media groups (Zimmerly and Badillo, 2016; Colussi and Rocha, 2020) or on the media in specific countries (Newman, Dutton, and Blank, 2012; Bosch, 2014; Ju, Jeong, and Chyi, 2014; Tous et al., 2015; Shao and Wang, 2017; Undurraga, 2017; Goyanes, López-López, and Demeter, 2021).

The third line of research focuses on the specific impact that social networks have on information professionals working in the media, focusing on aspects such as their gradual use as sources of information even by the most prestigious journalists (Krüger, 2015), which contrasts with the distrust with which these same reporters view them (Varona and Sánchez, 2016), in areas such as the guidelines for maintaining a conversation with receivers that breaks with their work routines (Whibey, Joseph, and Lazer, 2019), in location-based monitoring or the detection of possible informatively relevant events that require extreme caution (Thurman, 2018) and even underlining the possibility of the journalist becoming a global celebrity through its use (Newman, 2009).

Additionally, their effects on the journalistic task are examined in terms of the typology of specific networks such as Twitter (Vergeer, 2015; Brems et al., 2017; Molyneux and McGregor, 2021), Facebook (Welbers and Opgenhaffen, 2019; Meese and Hurcombe, 2021; Lamot 2022), Instagram (Vázquez, Direito, and López-García, 2019; Bainotti, Caliandro, and Gandini, 2021; Sormanen, Reinikainen, and Wilska, 2022) or YouTube (Borah, Fowler, and Ridout, 2018; Jaakkola, 2018; Lichtenstein, Herbers, and Bause, 2021).

Analyses focused on audiences include contributions on how their multinational nature allows them to influence local media markets (Heidemann, Klier, and Probst, 2012) and how they erode levels of data privacy (Tucker, 2013), as well as works that highlight how giving their users previously unknown possibilities of interaction and generation of their own content forces the media to take them into consideration (Haythornthwaite, 2005; Loosen and Schmidt, 2012) or that focus on how they establish new counterweights between media and audiences (Fu, 2016) or address the case of younger population groups that over the last decades the media have had difficulties in accessing and building loyalty (Clark and Marchi, 2017).

We also find their consideration as elements that contribute to question the maintenance of the quality levels of the contents generated by the journalistic editorial staff in the face of the invasion of messages of inane nature (Marchionni, 2013; Denisova, 2022) or that cause the rupture of the binomial formed by media and receivers sponsoring the process of disintermediation of the information industry (Picard, 2014; Moreno and Sepúlveda, 2021).

The last of these research lines refers to the consideration of social networks as strategic instruments for the promotion and dissemination of all kinds of hoaxes and false contents with contributions that focus on their relevance for the irruption of the post-truth phenomenon (Carrera, 2018; De Blasio and Selva, 2021), in the facet to exercise as distorting elements of reality through the presentation of biased content (Rapp and Salovich, 2018; Tsang, 2021) or in their role as reinforcers of prejudices by means of the repetition of messages (Britt et al., 2019; Rhodes, 2022).

This fact is accelerated since October 2019 with the emergence and expansion of the COVID-19 global pandemic. Experience to date highlights the extent to which they have become resonance loudspeakers that promote the dissemination of a wide range of hoaxes about this disease (Salaverría et al., 2020; Papadopoulou and Maniou, 2021), contribute to a deterioration in the credibility of the media, which on

many occasions echo their contents without the necessary verification (Apuke and Omar, 2021; Ceron et al., 2021) and, for some authors, even lay the foundations for a process of information warfare of a global and hybrid nature (Gaber and Fisher, 2022).

Method

Despite this extensive bibliography, to date there are no quantitative studies of a global nature referring to transnational realities that focus exclusively on the analysis of the real specific weight of social networks as channels for the generation of web traffic to cybermedia. None of the research presented in the scientific literature examines the percentage of cybermedia web traffic corresponding to social networks.

We believe that this type of study is not only interesting to the information industry itself, but also to researchers in digital journalism and to those in charge of university teaching centers that aspire to incorporate scientific knowledge of social networks by journalism professionals in their new curricula.

Research questions

Given this fact, we posed four research questions:

RQ1: What percentage of the total web traffic generated by European Union cybermedia is coming from social networks?

RQ2: Is this percentage higher or lower than that provided by direct traffic and through the use of search engines via SEO positioning?

RQ3: Which social networks have a greater impact on information industry?

RQ4: Is there any relationship between the specific weight of social networks in the web traffic of a cybermedia and circumstances such as the average duration of a user's visit, the number of page views or the bounce rate (understood in its formal facet of not carrying out any kind of interaction on the page visited beyond reading its content)?

Cybermedia selection

To answer these questions, we first made a selection of the cybermedia with the highest web traffic in the 27 countries that are currently part of the European Union after the United Kingdom leaves on December 31, 2020. In each nation we have selected five media using a combination of global web traffic metrics provided by the tools Alexa (<https://www.alexa.com/>), which ceased to be operational on May 1, 2022, and SimilarWeb (<https://www.similarweb.com/>). We have not used local metrics by country since the results obtained with these first two tools were enough significant and our objective is not to establish a ranking of cybermedia by nation but to examine the relevance of social networks in their web traffic.

In all cases, we have selected cybermedia owned by a journalistic company, discarding those belonging to telecommunications portals or service providers; in some cases they correspond to classic information

companies (both newspapers and television stations) while in others they refer to digital natives, without this circumstance affecting the nature of the research proposed. We can see the selected media in chart number 1.

Chart 1. Selected cybermedia belonging to 27 EU countries

We then proceeded to examine the web traffic data of these cybermedia. We selected the period corresponding to the months of October, November and December 2021 and January, February and March 2022. We consider that this six-month period allows us to overcome possible variations during a month, reinforcing the accuracy of the data obtained.

To obtain this data we have used the SimilarWeb tool, currently the most accurate one available for examining the web traffic of a site, although it is limited to traffic coming from desktops and laptops without taking into account those coming from mobile devices, which are currently impossible to determine with existing measurement tools on the market.

The choice of this tool responds to the fulfillment of the requirements of proven robustness, remarkable flexibility in its configuration and accredited capacity for the generation of reliable data, as well as its effective use in different research in the field of social sciences in general and communication and journalism in particular: analysis of security levels in the flow of news content of The Guardian and The New York Times on the occasion of the Snowden case (Thorsen, 2017), comparative study of disruptive processes in journalistic production in Germany, Australia and the United Kingdom (Schapals, Maares, and Hanusch, 2019), examination of the impact of digital transformation on the information ecosector (Mas and Gómez, 2021) or analysis of fake removal information advertisement on an international scale (Koide et al., 2021), among others.

We also found the use of SimilarWeb for the specific study of the influence of social networks in facets such as communication in Spanish hospitals (González et al., 2021), public opinion in Turkey (Gargouri, 2022) or the population group of teenagers (González, Martínez, and Arenas, 2022).

The results are obtained from the average of the five most popular cybermedia considered in each of the 27 countries of the European Union. They are grouped into four items:

Percentage of traffic generated from social networks over total web traffic in each EU country

Comparison of web traffic generated from social networks with direct and search procedures in each EU country

Main social networks by web traffic generated in each EU country

General data referring to the average duration of the user's visit (expressed in minutes and seconds), number of page views and bounce rate

Results

Traffic generated from social networks over total web traffic in each EU country

Chart 2 shows the varied percentage of web traffic directly attributable to social networks in each of the 27 EU countries examined, ranging from a minimum of 4.97% in Spain to a maximum of 18.96% in Denmark, which is almost four times the previous figure. Among the nations with a lower impact index (below 7%) are Italy (5.09%), Germany (5.88%), Bulgaria and Czech Republic (6.19%), Greece (6.56%), France (6.82%) and Sweden (6.88%) while the States with higher percentages (above 15%) are Hungary (17.89%), Slovenia (15.83%) and Malta (15.59%).

The figures obtained do not show any relationships related to geographical and/or cultural affinity. In the case of the Benelux countries, compared to Luxembourg and Netherlands with 8.04% and 8.07% respectively, there is Belgium with 13.10%. 10%,; in the former Eastern European countries the examples of Bulgaria and Czech Republic (6.19%), Slovakia (8.31%), Poland (9.01%) and Croatia (9.78%) contrast with those of Hungary (17.89%), Slovenia (15.83%) and Romania (12.22%).

On the other hand, in the Mediterranean arc nations the low impact of Spain (4.97%), Italy (5.08%), Greece (6.56%) or France (6.82%) has not relationship with the much higher impact of Malta (15.59%) and Cyprus (10.67%), while recognizing the island peculiarity of the latter two; considerable differences are also perceived in the Baltic States with Latvia (8.62%) and Estonia (10.49%) far below Lithuania (13.85%); and such disparity of figures also concerns the Nordic countries since the percentages of Sweden (6.88%) or even Finland (10.48%) have nothing to do with those of Denmark (18.96%).

Comparison of web traffic generated from social networks with direct and search procedures in each EU country

Chart 3 shows that the specific weight of social networks as web traffic generation tools is always lower than that of direct traffic and search procedures based on SEO strategies. This general principle has two exceptions when the comparison is made between social networks and search procedures, concerning Denmark (18.96% for social networks versus 13.30% for search procedures) and Hungary (17.89% and 15.40% for social networks and search procedures respectively).

In all nations the relevance of direct traffic is much higher than that of social networks, with Italy, Germany, Sweden and Austria standing out, where this difference is at least nine times higher. The lowest percentage difference between the two magnitudes is found in Hungary, Romania, Slovenia and Malta, all below the four-to-one ratio.

With the two exceptions indicated above, the comparison between social networks and search procedures shows a lower specific weight of the former in relation to the latter. This lower relevance is between more

than seven to one in Spain and France, and less than two to one for Cyprus, Latvia, Lithuania, Malta, Slovenia and Estonia.

As shown in the previous table, no impact related to geographical proximity and cultural affinity has been detected (the low ratios of the Baltic countries in the comparison between social networks and search procedures are not considered to be scientifically relevant for the analysis here).

Main social networks by web traffic generated in each EU country

Chart 4 shows that in all countries Facebook is the main social network for generating traffic to the websites of the European Union's cybermedia with a maximum percentage of 93.26% for Hungary and a minimum of 42.70% for Germany. Above 90% are Slovakia (91.34%), Estonia (91.29%) and Malta (90.99%); at the lower end (less than 50%) are Netherlands (48.27%) and Ireland (47.82%).

As in the two previous tables, there are no geographical and/or cultural coincidences in the set of figures extracted.

The only exception to the primacy of Facebook is Spain, where the main social network is Twitter (44.09%) and Facebook reaches a 30.80% of the total.

Twitter is the second social network for its possibility to generate web traffic in 18 of the EU countries studied, followed by YouTube (in 6 nations), with the least frequent cases being Draugiem (in Latvia) and Reddit (in Romania).

Among the three social networks with the greatest impact, there is only one Pinterest mention (third place in Greece) and none of well-known platforms such as Instagram or LinkedIn.

Other relevant data

The data reflected in chart 5 are an additional contribution referring to the magnitudes of average duration of the user's visit (expressed in minutes and seconds), number of page views and bounce rate, so that no extrapolations can be made from them referring to the specific weight of social networks as tools for generating web traffic to the EU cybermedia.

In general terms, a longer duration of visits implies a higher number of page views per user, although there is no exact correlation between both magnitudes: Slovenia and Lithuania are the only two countries with a duration of more than 7 minutes, while Cyprus and Ireland are the ones with the shortest duration of less than 3 minutes. In terms of page views per visitor, Lithuania is the only country that exceeds the threshold of 4, while only Ireland, France and Romania are below the 2.50 level.

No direct or inverse relationship can be detected between the first two figures (average visit duration and pages per visit) and the third one (bounce rate). Regarding the latter, France is the only country that

exceeds 60%, while Denmark, Croatia, Finland, Slovakia and Estonia are the countries below 45%.

Conclusions

From the total web traffic from desktops and laptops that is generated among the European Union cybermedia with the highest number of unique visitors, just 9.858% is directly attributable to social networks. This percentage varies greatly from country to country, ranging from a low 4.97% for Spain to a high 18.96% for Denmark. Among the countries with a lower impact index (below 7%) are Italy (5.09%), Germany (5.88%), Bulgaria and Czech Republic (6.19%), Greece (6.56%), France (6.82%) and Sweden (6.88%), while the countries with the highest percentages (above 15%) are Hungary (17.89%), Slovenia (15.83%) and Malta (15.59%).

The figures obtained do not reveal any relationships related to geographical, cultural or political proximity, as evidenced by the differences between the nations considered, which are perceived in the Benelux countries, countries of the former Eastern Europe, Mediterranean nations, Baltic States or Nordic countries, among other possible combinations to be taken into account.

In general terms, the specific weight of social networks as a strategic instrument for generating web traffic from desktops and laptops to the UE cybermedia is lower than that of direct traffic and search procedures based on SEO strategies. Compared to the aforementioned percentage of 9.858% for social networks, we note 54.493% and 26.041% in the respective cases of direct traffic and search procedures.

In all EU countries the relevance of direct traffic is much higher than that of social networks, with Italy, Germany, Sweden and Austria standing out, where the difference is at least nine times higher. The lowest percentage difference between the two magnitudes corresponds to Hungary, Romania, Slovenia and Malta, all below the four to one ratio.

A comparison between social networks and search procedures shows that in twenty five countries the latter generate more traffic than the former, with Spain and France at the top with a ratio of one to seven and Cyprus, Latvia, Lithuania, Malta, Slovenia and Estonia at the bottom with less than one to two; the only exceptions are Denmark (18.96% for social networks versus 13.30% for search procedures) and Hungary (17.89% and 15.40% for social networks and search procedures respectively).

Among the three social networks with the greatest impact, there is only one Pinterest mention (third place in Greece) and none of well known platforms such as Instagram or LinkedIn.

The main social network that generates web traffic to the cybermedia with the highest number of unique visitors is Facebook in twenty six of the twenty seven countries of the European Union. However, there are notable differences between the countries considered, with a maximum percentage of 93.26% for Hungary's online media and a minimum of 42.70% in the case of Germany. Above 90% are Slovakia (91.34%), Estonia (91.29%) and Malta (90.99%); at the lower end (less than 50%) are Netherlands (48.27%) and Ireland (47.82%).

The only exception to the almost complete primacy of Facebook is in Spain, where the main network is Twitter with 44.09% and where Facebook reaches a 30.80% of the total.

Twitter is the second social network in eighteen of the EU countries studied, followed by YouTube (in six nations), with the least frequent cases being Draugiem (Latvia) and Reddit (Romania).

The consideration of magnitudes such as average duration of the user's visit (expressed in minutes and seconds), number of page views and bounce rate does not allow us to extract any relationship on their potential impact on the web traffic generated by social networks in the cybermedia of the European Union with a higher number of unique visitors.

In general terms, a longer duration of visits implies a higher number of page views per user, although there is no exact correlation between both magnitudes; likewise, no direct or inverse relationship can be detected between average visit duration and pages per visit versus bounce rate. In relation to the latter, France is the only country that exceeds 60%, while Denmark, Croatia, Finland, Slovakia and Estonia are the countries below 45%.

Given this set of data, it is worth asking whether the large amount of human and economic resources that the media allocate to the management of their social networks as tools that allow them to generate web traffic is justified, as well as the constant and deep debate generated around the impact that social networks have on the shaping of public opinion and their incidence in phenomena such as disinformation or disintermediation.

Although this study should be completed with data corresponding to web browsing using mobile devices such as smartphones and tablets, to date there are no reliable measurement systems of a global nature, which makes difficult a scientific approach to this market segment.

Declarations

Declaration of Conflicting Interests

The authors declared no potential conflicts of interest respect to the research, authorship and/or publication of this article.

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Chart 1 To 5

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